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EMBEDDING A PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY FRAMEWORK INTO FACULTY WITH SEVERAL DISCIPLINES - A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Identity in engineering education has gained interest as a construct to improve academic attainment and retention, and to encourage students to graduate into engineering careers. Engineering identity is distinct and related to the constructs of motivation and self-efficacy. Many engineering faculty explicitly influence students' engineering identity development through skills inventories, and provide opportunities for enhanced skill development by reflective learning exercises. We report a case study describing how we introduced a novel professional identity framework into an engineering faculty which offers degree programmes across several disciplines. We describe its structure which comprises of four dimensions: Accreditation, Institution, Habits of Mind, and Career, with each dimension being characterised by a distinct skill inventory. We discuss our tactics for embedding this framework into an established setting, and explore some of its immediate benefits; monitoring skill progression across students years by self-ratings, measuring staff comprehension and engagement via the coding of their module descriptions, and measuring student understanding via the automatic natural language processing of student reflections on how their identity is progressing. Our framework and its embedding has the potential to encourage engineering faculty to think beyond accreditation requirements during programme development, improve module designs, and motivate students' skill development and career choice.

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1 INTRODUCTION

How can students' identification as engineers be explicitly encouraged and successfully embedded into engineering schools, and what is the benefit? The Cambridge dictionary defines identity as "who a person is, or the qualities of a person or group that make them different from others". Engineering identity is distinct to other constructs that yield similar benefits e.g. motivation and self-efficacy [1]. In education, whether students see themselves as engineers influences their academic performance and career choice [2]. Likewise, engineering schools' consideration of engineering identity enables them to better understand their students, widen participation, and improve career destinations [3]. Our incentive is to better understand how to forge engineering identity in order to improve these outcomes, which contributes to solving STEM skills shortages that limit productivity growth in economies [4].

We present a case study for embedding a "Professional Identity Framework" into an engineering faculty which runs programmes for several disciplines at undergraduate and post-graduate level. It consists of a skill inventory grouped into a novel categorisation scheme of four "dimensions". We survey related literature on identity (section 2), outline the framework structure and some embedding activities (section 3), and evaluate its usefulness on a cohort of 513 students (section 4).

2 ENGINEERING IDENTITY

2.1 Definitions

Defining engineering identity and its progression has gained interest over the last decade. A recent systematic literature review of engineering identity [5] highlights several definitions and inconsistent relationships to the underlying social science. Common social science theories cited are Communities of Practice [6] and Cultural World Theory [7]. These theories emphasise environment and social norms as key factors for identity development. Many identity studies in STEM education define identity according to Carlone and Johnson's conceptual model [8] which comprises three overlapping aspects of identity: social, personal, and domain. Quantitative measures of student identity based on this model are realised through survey instruments e.g. [9]. Alternatively, student perceptions of their identity can be captured and developed through essay writing in engineering ethics modules e.g. [10].

2.2 Social, Personal and Domain Identities

The concept of social identity originates from Erikson's Self Identity Theory [11] [12]. The theory proposes that an individual identity is conceived through group membership e.g. the feeling of belonging to engineering faculty, the university, and to the engineering professional bodies. Multiple Identity Theory [13] proposes that your identity is continually reconstructed from four aspects: Nature i.e. biology; Institutional i.e. roles defined by institutions; Discursive i.e. how people interact with you; Affinity i.e. your feeling of belonging to groups.

Domain identity is dependent on a student’s perceived performance, recognition, interest and competence in their subject [14]. The engineering domain may be considered to have constituents from its foundational subjects of maths, physics and science. Analysis of the 2011 Sustainability and Gender in Engineering (SaGE) survey of 6772 US college students revealed that engineering students have stronger physics and science identities compared to maths identities, and differ from science students in having more global agency [15].

3 PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY FRAMEWORK

3.1 Structure

Building on Carlone and Johnson’s model for student identity comprising personal, social and domain identities [8], we embed it into faculty (*Fig. 1*). The Engineer aspect of student identity (left plane expanded in the middle plane) is characterised by the student’s subject interest, recognition, ability and performance [14]. The embedding framework (right plane) comprises of four dimensions:

- A. Accreditation: The learning outcomes of an accredited degree.
- B. Institutional: General skills and competences desired by the University for all students.
- C. Habits of Mind: Thinking patterns associated with engineering professionals.
- D. Career: Consideration of future identity and career.

Figure 1 Professional Identity Framework for Engineering Identity

Each dimension has an underlying skills inventory. For Dimension A, Accreditation, these are learning outcomes for science and mathematics; Engineering analysis; Design; Economic, legal, social and environmental context; Engineering practice; Additional “transferable” general skills. Dimension B, Institution, covers the general and professional skills not fully defined by engineering accreditation as noted in [16]. Typically these skills reflect the local university priorities. Common skills for the Institution dimension include research-informed instruction [17] and developing Enterprise skills e.g. using the learning outcomes specified by the EU EntreComp Framework [18] [19]. Dimension C, Habits of Mind, concerns thinking patterns or competencies; automatic behaviours cultivated through constant repetition and reward throughout study. These describe how students approach complex challenges and are distinct from professional skills of Dimension B. We adopt the Royal Academy of Engineering (RAE) “Engineering Habits of Mind” model [4] formulated from extensive work with industry and higher education stakeholders. It defines six habits: systems

thinking, problem-finding, improving, creative problem solving and adaptability. Dimension D, Career, concerns students exploring their future identities for their skills for sectors and roles of interest. Building on work in [20], these recognise the different degree tracks and module choices through programmes tailored to their career aspirations e.g. Engineering Science for PhD, Engineering Design for Industry, Engineering Management for engineering consultancy, Policy/Society for government roles.

3.2 Embedding

To embed the framework into faculty, we develop a strategy following activities outlined in the “Five Dimensions of Growth” proposed by Costa and Kallick who pioneered Habits of Mind in pre-university education [21]. Some examples of stages relating to activities reported in section 4 are:

- Exploring Meanings:
 - Student exercises to build analogies to their own experiences around skills in the inventory including self-rating themselves against the skills (section 4.1) and reflecting on their coursework (section 4.3).
 - Academic teaching staff exercises to reword and rephrase skill descriptors to encourage adoption, plus training on aligning mapping their own teaching to the framework (section 4.2)

Other Stages and their Activities which maybe of interest to the reader but not further reported in this paper include:

- Increasing Alertness:
 - Environmental cues are introduced in the virtual and physical learning spaces. These include infographics videos and posters designed to activate engagement.
- Value Extending:
 - Existing reward and recognition systems incorporate the framework.

4 EVALUATION

We explore evidence to support the framework to answer the main research question posed in the introduction: How can students’ identification as engineers be explicitly encouraged and successfully embedded into engineering schools, and what is the benefit? Three aspects are explored:

- 1) Student self-rating of skills: How do students rate themselves against the PIFs four dimensions? This enables the comparison between cohorts at different levels to characterise progression from non-engineer to engineer.
- 2) Staff engagement and comprehension: How do educators relate the PIF to their teaching? This enables us to identify how educators understand the PIF and which elements are favoured.
- 3) Student reflection on identity progression: How does the PIF help students progress their engineering identities? This allows better formulation of how each element is described through automatic analysis of student’s language use.

4.1 Student self-rating of skills

As part of their yearly academic reviews, students from all undergraduate cohorts ($n=513$) were asked to rate themselves against each skill in each dimension using a five-point likert scale. The summary results (Fig 2.) reveal that, on average, first year Undergraduate students (UG1) rate themselves as differently than those in future years (UG2+). For Dimension A, the older cohort rated themselves as more skilled in Engineering design and analysis, yet less skilled in science and mathematics. For Dimension B (Institution) and C (Habits of Mind), the non-uniform differences for each skill between years potentially reveals the institution’s programmes relative strength and weakness, but notably, older year groups are more conservative in estimating their skill levels. This could be demonstrating the Dunning-Kruger effect [22], a cognitive bias where low ability people overestimate their ability. For Dimension D (Career), results suggest that as students progress, they became more attracted to research and managerial roles, reflecting the emphasis on research-led teaching and encouraging student leadership skills to differentiate itself with others.

Fig. 2 Student self-rating of skills against each dimension’s skill inventory

4.2 Staff engagement and comprehension

To measure staff engagement and comprehension, staff are asked to redraft their module descriptions and relate them to the framework. Redrafted descriptions are binary coded in 3 axes: whether they identify the relevant skills, whether they identify the relevant dimensions, and whether they contextualise the identified skills and dimensions in terms of the module content. 24 module descriptions are coded. An example of a redrafted module description which contextualises the framework for the module content would be: “Dimension A: The module applies science and maths

to give the understanding of the behaviour of fluids and energy, which underpins engineering design.”. In contrast, an example where the framework is not contextualised to module content would be “Dimension A: science, maths and engineering design”.

Coding revealed that 18 of the 24 responses directly refer to the Dimensions in the framework. 12 of these 18 also contextualise the identified skills or dimensions. Of these 12, 8 do it with respect to both skills and dimensions, whereas 3 do it with respect to dimensions only rather than the skills. For the remaining 12 that didn't contextualise the identified skills or dimensions, 5 listed only the skills. The remaining 7 who didn't contextualise listed the skills and dimensions together without distinction. The results suggest that staff find it easier to relate their modules to engineering identity when considering the four dimensions in addition to, or instead of, detailed skills inventories.

4.3 Student reflections on identity progression

Students ($n=513$) from all year groups are asked to reflect on a favourite item of coursework in terms of how they think it progresses their engineering identity for each dimension. *Table 1* gives an example of a student reflection and the number of responses for each dimension. In total, 2029 responses were analysed. Dimension A, Accreditation, attracts the largest number of responses, closely followed by Dimension C, Habits of mind. This suggests that students find it easy to relate their work to these two dimensions most strongly aligned to Engineering. Conversely, Dimension B, Institution, was the weakest attracting 10% fewer reflections. This could suggest that students find professional skills more difficult to reflect upon against specific pieces of learning, and/or the comprehension of local-generated skill inventories are inferior to those from national and global bodies. Dimension D, Careers, is also less reflected upon suggesting that not all students are career planning or see its relevance to coursework.

Table 1 Student reflections on identity progression

PIF Dimension	Number of Responses	Representative example of a student's reflective commentary.
Dimension A: Accreditation	526	<i>“This work has enabled me to apply my engineering analysis skills and also relate my chosen topic into a wider world context, something which I have only done in a limited way before”</i>
Dimension B: Institution	481	<i>“Research informed - I have explored my chosen topic in greater depth in writing this report.”</i>
Dimension C: Habits of Mind	520	<i>“Problem Finding - Clarifying needs, checking existing solutions, investigating contexts, verifying.”</i>
Dimension D: Career	502	<i>“Discovering new knowledge, collecting and analysing data and using digital data technologies.”</i>

We compare vocabulary usage in the responses to determine whether there are differences between dimensions. 2724 distinct words are identified from the

responses. They are processed using established Automatic Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques [23] in the following sequential steps:

- 1) Responses are corrected by hand for spelling and grammatical errors.
- 2) The sentence text is tokenised into individual words for analysis.
- 3) The text is shortened using stop word removal to eliminate common every day words such as “a”, “it”, “and”, etc.
- 4) Morphological variation in word use is reduced using Stemming and Lemmatization.

The algorithms were used the NLTK toolkit in Python 3 [24]. An example of processed text against each step is shown in *Table 2*.

Table 2 Natural Language Processing of Student reflections

Step	Example Processed Text
Original text	i demonstrated my research skills using the harvard referencing format
Original text after Stop-word removal.	demonstrated research skills using harvard referencing format
Stop-word text after Stemming.	demonstr research skill use harvard referenc format
Stop-word text after Lemmatization.	demonstrated research skill using harvard referencing format

Once the text is processed and morphological variation reduced through stemming of lemmatization, individual word counts for each response were tallied for each dimension and compared. *Fig. 3* shows the results for lemmatized text.

Fig. 3 Top 20 Word Count Distributions for each Dimension using Lemmatized text

Notably, each dimension’s most popular word is different. Accreditation: “design”; Institution: “research”; Habits of Mind: “problem”; Career: “skill”. Other words’ relative popularities helps to determine whether the framework and distinctions between dimensions are comprehended by the student body. Word counts for stemmed and stop-word responses achieve similar results to the lemmatized responses. To further understand the differences in vocabulary use between dimensions, the term frequency – inverse document frequency (tf-idf) is computed for each word. This measure calculates how important the term (word), t , is in a specific document, d , given a collection of N_D documents i.e. the corpus:

$$tf_idf(t, d) = tf(t, d) * \log\left(\frac{N_D}{df(t)+1}\right) \quad (1).$$

Where $tf(t,d)$ is the term frequency – which is computed from the count t in the document in proportion to the overall count of t in the corpus:

$$tf(t, d) = N_{t,d}/N_t \quad (2).$$

And $df(t)$ is the document frequency – the proportion of documents in which the term occurs:

$$df(t) = N_{d,t}/N_D \quad (3).$$

In this context, terms are individual words, the document represents all text in the responses for a specific dimension, and the corpus is all dimensions. The results of computing the tf-idf for words having the highest scores are shown in *Table 3*. Each row highlights the highest scoring dimension for that word. Notably, the top four words correspond to different dimensions.

Table 3: tf-idf scores for words used by students

Word	Dimension			
	Accreditation	Institution	Habits of Mind	Career
research	0.07	0.43	0.10	0.22
skill	0.38	0.35	0.21	0.41
design	0.40	0.14	0.32	0.10
problem	0.13	0.29	0.37	0.09
engineering	0.37	0.12	0.16	0.24
work	0.25	0.30	0.30	0.31
industry	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.29
career	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.23
project	0.17	0.21	0.20	0.17
smart	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.19

5 SUMMARY

We proposed an professional identity framework for engineering students. Our evaluation shows that it provides a means to measure skill progression, and validates the distinction and usefulness of grouping skills under the four dimensions of Accreditation, Institution, Habits of Mind, and Career. This framework can be used to broaden programme development beyond meeting accreditation requirements, provide educators with perspectives to reframe teaching to consider identity formation, and help students motivate their studies and career choices.

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